

THE FLOWATCH-PROJECT: MEASURING WATER, CARBON DIOXIDE AND ENERGY FLUXES AT THE FIELD SCALE

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ABSTRACT

The FLOWatch test site has been established to investigate the relationship between field scale (effective) fluxes of water, energy and carbon dioxide and the spatial variations of these fluxes within the field. The variability of water, energy and carbon dioxide fluxes within the field is strongly related to the spatial variations of the soil water content. Therefore, a range of soil water content measurement techniques will be used within the FLOWatch project. For monitoring soil surface water content at the field scale a feasibility study was conducted using two different ground penetrating radar methods. Namely, the WARR (Wide Angle and Reflection and Refraction) method and its possibility of mapping the soil water content with the ground wave of the GPR signal, and second, the monostatic far-field ground penetrating radar system. Both systems were compared with ground truth measurements from time domain reflectometry, frequency domain reflectometry, and volumetric soil samples in two measurement campaigns. The results showed, that the ground wave method was not successful and that the far-field method is not comparable with standard soil physical soil water content measurement techniques. The main reason for the failure of the ground wave method was the strong attenuation of the GPR signal, which can be related to the loamy texture at the test site. The major problem in the comparison of the soil water contents derived from monostatic far-field GPR and TDR or volumetric soil sample measurements can be drawn to differences in the observation depth and sampling volume. Nevertheless, the far-field GPR approach seems to be a promising tool for imaging the shallow subsurface and to identify dielectric properties and soil water content.

1. INTRODUCTION

For water, energy and CO₂ fluxes in agricultural landscapes, the field scale plays a crucial role since it corresponds to the scale at which humans directly influence fluxes by managing the system for crop cultivation. This leads to a human-induced spatio-temporal variability of these fluxes at the regional scale. Consequently, the field scale is considered as the elementary scale for modelling of water, CO₂ and energy fluxes. Despite intensive research in the past, there is still a lack in knowledge concerning the spatial and temporal interdependency of soil state variables (e.g. moisture, soil temperature), matter fluxes

Date: 28.02.2006.

from soil and vegetation in the atmosphere (e.g. water, carbon dioxide) as well as their variability and respective effective values at the field scale. The FLOWatch project aims to improve our understanding of the spatial and temporal variability of water, energy and carbon dynamics in the soil and their role in determining effective evapotranspiration and carbon exchange fluxes at the field scale. To this end, micrometeorological, geophysical and (ground-based) remote sensing methods will be combined with mechanistic models describing the dynamics of water, energy and CO₂ in soils.

Modelling of C-dynamics involves the description of the turn-over of different organic matter pools. The turnover rates depend on soil temperature, soil water content, and soil CO₂ concentration amongst others. Therefore, an accurate representation of these state variables is a key issue for the predictive modelling of carbon turnover and CO₂ efflux. Within the FLOWatch project, several non-invasive and soil physical methods will be implemented to measure soil water content at different scales. At the point scale, far-field ground penetrating radar (GPR), electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), and time domain reflectometry (TDR) will be used. For plot scale estimates of soil water content, a passive L-band radiometer will be installed. To obtain a spatial representation of the energy balance components, meteorological measurements will be combined with 2D soil surface temperature images from an IR-camera. Spatial and temporal variability of CO₂ fluxes will be measured with automated soil CO₂ flux systems (LICOR Biosciences). Temporal variability of the CO₂ flux at the plot scale will be measured using the eddy covariance method when conditions allow it. For the modelling of the water balance, the energy balance and the CO₂ efflux, a model containing the following processes will be used: (I) water and heat transport in variably saturated soils, (II) organic carbon turnover based on with multiple pools with variable turnover rates, (III) multiphase CO₂ transport from the soil to the atmosphere.

In this paper, the experimental setup of the FLOWatch-Project and first results of a feasibility study of two different GPR-approaches (GPR-ground-wave and monostatic far-field GPR) will be presented.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. FLOWatch test site. The FLOWatch test site of the Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH is situated in the southern part of the Lower Rhine Embayment in Germany. The underlying sediments are Quaternary sediments, which are mostly fluvial deposits from Rhine/Maas river and the Rur river system, covered by eolian sediments (up to a depth of 1 m) from Pleistocene and Holocene. In the lower part of the test site, colluvial sediments eroded from the upper part can be found. The ground water depth shows seasonal fluctuation from 1 to 3 m below the surface. The test site is weakly inclined (2°) in east west direction (Figure 1). The soil surface is mainly composed of loess with a high silt content (>70%). Some gravels are present in the upper (Eastern) part of the site. The soil type is silt loam, according to the U.S. Department of Agriculture textural classification. Due to the geomorphology and texture, a high variability in the soil surface water content is detectable. In general, the upper part of the test site shows lower soil surface water contents compared to the lower part (Figure 1). The experimental field plot (15 x 15 m) is situated in the lower part of the test site. At one site of the experimental field plot a trench is located with an extent of 13.5 m in horizontal and 1.2 m in vertical spacing.

Overall 100 TDR-probes (3-rod probes with a length of 20 cm) were installed, whereby 60 TDR-probes were inserted in 10 vertical columns of 6 probes each. Additionally, 40 TDR-probes were installed in 5 vertically nests to gain information of the short distance soil water variability. All TDR-probes were connected to a Campbell TDR100 system and logged in 2 h intervalls. In addition to the soil water measurements TDR-probes were calibrated for electrical conductivity measurements. For the information of the ambient matric potential 18 tensiometers (T4, UMS-München) with a shaft length of 20 cm were installed in 3 vertical columns. Additionally, 18 pF-Meter (EcoTech-Bonn, shaft length = 20 cm) were inserted to measure ambient soil matric potential and soil temperature. Both measurement devices (tensiometers and pF-Meters) were installed close to each other to compare results from the different methods. For soil temperature measurements another 18 Pt100 thermo-elements were buried in 3 vertical columns. To extract soil water for the direct measurement of the soil water electrical conductivity 12 suction cups were installed randomly. All measurements for matric potential and soil temperature were logged in 10 min. intervalls. The aim of the trench is to measure the spatial and temporal variability of the state variables soil water content, θ , soil temperature, T , and bulk electrical conductivity, σ . These data will be used for the validation of the GPR and ERT results as well as for the 1 and 2D models for water, CO_2 , and energy flux dynamics.

FIGURE 1. FLOWatch test site (a) with elevation and surface soil water content measured with 20 cm TDR-probe at 140 points (b) (data 18th May 2005).

2.2. GPR-measurements. To obtain the soil water content of the soil surface layer ground penetrating radar (GPR) seems to be a promising approach. In general, three different approaches in the GPR technique are available to map soil water content non-invasively. First, the commonly used method of the analysis of the reflected wave [3] [10] which requires implicit knowledge of the depth of the reflection for absolute water content calculations. The second method is the analysis of the ground wave [1] [3] [4], where the

sampling volume of water content measurement depends on the antenna separation. Finally, the monostatic far-field approach described by [5], [6], [7] and [8]. In our feasibility study the GPR-ground-wave approach and the monostatic far-field approach were tested at the FLOWatch test site between May and June 2005.

In our experimental setup, an off-ground GPR which is based on full-wave inversion of the GPR signal in the frequency domain for an off-ground monostatic configuration was chosen due to its possibility to measure soil surface water content at the point scale without soil contact and destruction of vegetation. Following the approach of [5], [6], [7] and [8], an ultrawide band stepped-frequency continuous-wave radar combined with an off-ground monostatic transverse electromagnetic (TEM) horn antenna was used. The radar system was set up using a vector network analyzer (VNA) connecting to an antenna system consisted of a linear polarized double-ridged broadband TEM horn. The antenna dimensions are 22 cm in length and 14 x 24 cm² aperture area. The nominal frequency range was 1-18 GHz. Measurements were performed with the antenna aperture situated at height from 20 to 30 cm above ground. The VNA was calibrated at the connection between the antenna feed point and the high quality N type 50 Ohm impedance coaxial cable of 2.5 m length. The modelling of the radar signal follows the procedure described by [5], and [6]. The corresponding transfer function, expressed in the frequency domain, is given by:

$$S_{11}(\omega) = \frac{b(\omega)}{a(\omega)} = H_i(\omega) + \frac{H(\omega)G_{xx}^\dagger(\omega)}{1 - H_f(\omega)G_{xx}^\dagger(\omega)} \quad (1)$$

where $b(\omega)$ and $a(\omega)$ are, respectively, the received and emitted signals at the VNA reference plane, $H_i(\omega)$ is the return loss, $H(\omega) = H_t(\omega)H_r(\omega)$ is the transmitting-receiving transfer function, $H_f(\omega)$ is the feedback loss, and $G_{xx}^\dagger(\omega)$ is the transfer Green's function of the air-subsurface system modeled as a three-dimensional multilayered medium.

As a second GPR method, the ground wave method was used.

For the measurements of the soil permittivity, ϵ_{soil} , and the calculation of the soil moisture content, the ground wave method as described by [3] [4] was used. In general, the ground wave is the part of the radiated energy that travels between the transmitter and receiver through the top of the soil. The most straightforward relationship between ground wave arrival time t_{GW} [s], antenna separation x [m] and soil permittivity is:

$$\epsilon_{GW} = \left(\frac{C}{v}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{C(t_{GW} - t_{AW}) + x}{x}\right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where t_{AW} [s] is the air wave arrival time, V is the single ground wave velocity and C the the speed of light in free space.

As reference ground truth measurements time domain reflectometry (TDR) and/or frequency domain reflectometry (FDR), and undisturbed soil samples (100 or 300 cm³ Kopecky-rings) were taken. As TDR system a Campbell TDR100 system (Campbell Scientific Ltd., Logan, Utah, USA) was chosen with a 3-rod probe of 10 cm length. For the TDR analysis the whole wave form was stored and analysed semi-automatically. For the FDR measurements a 6 cm Theta-probe (ML2x, DeltaT Devices Ltd., UK) was chosen, whereby only the millivoltage signal was stored and transferred to the dielectric permittivity afterwards. The calculation of the volumetric water content from dielectric

permittivities of the GPR, TDR, and FDR measurements were done by using Topp's equation [9]. The reference volumetric water content from the undisturbed soil samples were calculated after the standard procedure of oven drying at 105° for 48 h.

Preliminary to GPR measurements, the intensive research plot was plowed to a depth of 15 cm and compacted afterwards using a 50 cm large roller to reduce soil roughness. Due to low natural soil water contents one part of the test plot was irrigated to obtain a wider range in water contents. Measurements were performed every meter, resulting in 72 (8 x 9) radar measurements. Subsequently to each radar measurement, five juxtaposed Theta-probe measurements were performed in the area just beneath the antenna for measuring the soil dielectric permittivity (depth = 6 cm). Then, three 100 cm³ undisturbed soil samples were extracted at the same location but only one line on two, resulting in 36 measurement points. Detailed information of the experimental setup and data acquisition of the GPR system can be found in [8]. For the Theta-probe and the ground truth water content measurements, point averaged values are considered.

For the second measurement campaign 4 transects were measured along the y-axis of the test site. Next to the monostatic far-field GPR measurements, ground truth measurements using Theta-probe, TDR and 300 cm³ Kopecky-rings within the footprint of the antenna were taken. Overall, 48 measurement points for the Theta-probe, TDR and far-field GPR were taken. Kopecky-rings were only taken at each second measurement point. Ground wave measurements were taken continuously in 0.5 m distances at the transects resulting in 1188 measurement points. The spacing between the antenna and receiver was set fixed to 1.18 m. To reduce soil roughness the field was tilled up to a depth of 15 cm and compacted afterwards using a 2 tonne roller.

3. RESULTS

For the GPR feasibility study two measurement campaigns took place at the FLOWatch test site at the 21st of March 2005 and the 27th of July 2005. In the first campaign the intensive research plot was chosen to measure soil water content with the monostatic far-field GPR and ground truth measurements at 8 by 9 m scale. In the second experiment 4 transects along the y-axis of the test field were measured using both GPR systems and ground truth measurements.

3.1. Plot measurements. The results of the mapped soil water content at the intensive research plot measured with the far-field GPR method and the reference FDR-probe are plotted in Figure 2. In general, the dielectric permittivity, and calculated water contents using Topp's equation [9], are lower for GPR than the Theta-probe. This may be partly attributed to the effect of soil roughness on the amplitude of surface reflection. Another reason may be the vertical distribution of water content. The Theta-probe gives average values up to a depth of 6 cm, whereas the GPR measurements provide values for which the depth of influence is variable as a function of water content, and is therefore not precisely known. During the experiment the soil profile was characterized by a first drier layer in the upper 1.5 cm at the non-irrigated measurement points due to surface evaporation. If GPR is mainly sensitive to the upper part of the profile in the frequency range 1 - 18 GHz, this can explain the lower observed values for the dielectric permittivity and calculated water contents. This explanation can be confirmed by the fact that for the higher water

contents pertaining to the irrigated area, GPR and Theta-probe measurements provide similar results.

FIGURE 2. Volumetric water content (θ) maps obtained using far-field GPR (a) and Theta-probe (b) at the intensive research plot (data 21st March 2005).

3.2. Field measurements. The results of the measurements at the field scale in terms of volumetric water content are plotted in Figure 3. It can be seen that the maps based on

FIGURE 3. Volumetric water content (θ) maps obtained using far-field GPR, ground wave GPR, 10 cm TDR measurements, and 300 cm³ Kopecky-rings at the FLOWatch test site (data 27th July 2005).

the TDR measurements and the undisturbed soil samples both show a similar spatial trend

in soil water content. The soil water content measurements based on the ground wave and the far-field method deviate from the two other measurement techniques. In general, the ground wave method seems to overestimate the water content over the entire field. Also, the variation in soil water content is less for the ground wave method. Figure 4 shows two of the four ground wave GPR profiles, where the horizontal wave at approximately 14 ns corresponds with the air wave. Typically it is assumed that the ground wave is next arrival in the radargram. In the upper GPR profile (1 transect) between 20 and 50 m, a clear wave can be recognized. We assumed that this wave is the ground wave and picked the arrival times of the air and ground wave to calculate soil water content according to Equation 2. Figure 4 also shows that the ground wave is difficult to recognize in large parts of the GPR profile. Especially between 50 and 150 m in the 4 transect (lower GPR profile) no clear signal from the soil is detectable. Although there is a strong attenuated signal between 20 and 25 ns that we interpreted as the ground wave, the similarity with a similar feature between 18 and 20 ns could also indicate that the radargram is dominated by multiple critically refracted waves in this part of the profile. There are two main

FIGURE 4. Two ground wave GPR profiles measured with an antenna separation of 1.18 m at the FLOWatch test site (data 27th July 2005). The transects correspond with $Y = 0$ m and $Y = 24$ m in Figure 3.

reasons for the unsatisfying results of the ground wave method at the FLOWatch test site. The first and most important reason is the strong attenuation of the GPR signal in the lower part of the field. Attenuation is strongly related to soil water content and soil texture. As already stated by [2], soil with high silt and clay content are not always suitable for the ground wave method. The second reason for the failure of the ground wave method is the possible interference of shallow reflections. There is no guarantee that these reflections will not arrive even earlier in different parts of the field depending on variation of the shallow reflecting layers. An indication for the interference with reflected waves is given by different ground wave signatures in the left part of the GPR profiles shown in Figure 4. The discrepancy between far-field GPR and ground truth measurements are multiple. First, GPR and TDR operate at different scales and depth: a depth of ≈ 10 cm and an area of ≈ 30 cm² for TDR, and a depth of $\approx 1 - 5$ cm and an area of ≈ 720 cm²

for GPR. Since the soil surface was subject to evaporation during the measurements, the differences in depth scale would explain partly lower soil water contents observed by the GPR method. Finally, the far-field GPR measurements are affected by several factors. Surface roughness or stochastic heterogeneity of the soil electromagnetic properties may lead to diffuse reflection and scattering which are not accounted by the inverse modelling procedure. The presence of such phenomena can partly explain the lower soil water contents for far field GPR measurements. Then, in addition to the radar calibration and measurements errors, the shallow soil stratigraphy and soil electric conductivity are also important characteristics which can play a significant role.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility study of the two different GPR methods at the FLOWatch test site clearly showed that the ground wave method was not successful and that the far-field method is not comparable with standard soil physical soil water content measurement techniques. In general, the spatial variation in soil water content measured with the ground wave and far field method did not correspond with the variations measured with TDR and volumetric water content samples. The main reason for the failure of the ground wave method was the strong attenuation of the GPR signal, which is related to the loamy texture at the test site. The variations in the far-field mapping vs TDR and Kopecky-samples might be explained by differences in the sampling volume and depth. Nevertheless, the far-field GPR approach has proven to be a promising tool for imaging the shallow subsurface and identifying dielectric properties and water content. However, still several issues are to be investigated to better understand the various factors affecting the radar measurements. Therefore, laboratory experiments should be conducted and the results should be implemented into modelling approaches. Especially soil surface roughness and soil layering should be taken into account in the electromagnetic inverse modelling approach.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank R. Harms, H.G. Sittardt, P. Bauer-Gottwein and T. Pütz for their assistance in the measurements. We also want to thank the University of Amsterdam for the GPR system.

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